

AM4BAT PROJECT

Deliverable 8.5

Recycling study

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Executive summary

Task 8.4 have as objective to provide a recycling feasibility study of the new SSB generation developed in AM4BAT. The objective is to study all the recycling steps and minimize the use of pyrometallurgical treatments, especially during pretreatment steps to avoid Li losses. All recycling steps (deactivation, opening, active materials separation and recovery) will be studied on this battery generation, first to identify the possible main recycling behaviors or bottlenecks compared to traditional Li-ion battery. All recycling steps will be experimentally studied to prove the recyclability with full hydrometallurgical recycling process.

This catalogue is structured in two main parts:

- 1) Recycling study on separate materials from AM4BAT project: this part treats step by step from physical to chemical separation methods based on separate materials sent by AM4BAT partners
- 2) A proof of concept of recycling on AM4BAT pouch-cell

The defined flow sheet for recycling of AM4BAT pouch cell consists in multiple steps aimed at valorizing the main elements of the battery, excluding the casing whose proportion and composition are strongly dependent on the size of the manufactured object and generally easily recyclable. The developed process seeks to recover LiTFSI, LLZO or SiO₂, NMC, and metals that make up current collectors. No attention was paid to recycling the polymer parts since, being photopolymerized, it is difficult to recover the monomers. The process developed therefore seeks to recover these elements with the highest possible purity and recovery rate while minimizing the number of steps required in order to offer a simple and low-impact treatment flowsheet.

The use of physical separation steps other than grinding reduces the number of downstream steps by allowing certain layers to be separated during the primary stages. To achieve this, a dismantling step is considered, which allows the active parts of the casing to be extracted, followed by separation by screening and sink-float of the different layers before the use of hydrometallurgy.

While the steps developed are very effective for treating separated materials, applying these steps to the actual battery has revealed certain difficulties, although the recovery and purity obtained in an initial test were satisfactory. In particular, the separation of NMC particles from the electrolyte in the as-received EoL cell is incomplete. However, these two layers can be treated at the same time without taking into account the recovery of SiO₂, which is inexpensive and present in very small proportion.

The developed recycling procedure applied on AM4BAT anode type cell from AIT allowed the recovery of 87 % Li from LiTFSI in the form of LiTFSI-rich solution. Current collector's (Cu-Sn and Al) were completely solubilized thanks to physical and chemical steps. 67 % of copper content was then recovered in metallic form by electrowinning with purity of 99.55 %. Complete Cu deposition can be easily achieved if longer times are applied or bigger electrode surface is used. Considering NMC recovery from the real cell, an additional NaOH washing step

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was first carried on the powder to remove Al impurities. XRD pattern of the powder in addition to the SEM images confirm the NMC crystallographic structure and spherical morphology. Carbon impurities present in NMC cathode material are estimated by XRD at 8 wt.%.

As the chemistry of Am4bat cells is dependent on the project partner, the developed recycling steps are not adapted for all material types. In particular, the current collector can vary between Ag/Cu or Sn/Cu and therefore they will show different leaching behavior which can further influence the efficiency and the process adapted for their separation. Moreover, electrolytes used in this project are based on a polymeric matrix which can contain LLZO or SiO₂ or none of these oxides. As a function of the oxide used, the economic interest of the recovered products will be variable, such that LLZO (present in higher content) has a higher economical value than SiO₂.

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Introduction

Nowadays, li-ion batteries dominate the battery market but other alternatives are currently being developed to improve performances (increase energy density), reduce costs and mainly, enhance their safe handling. For example, substituting conventional liquid electrolytes with solid ones would reduce the risk of leakage and therefore battery fires, also there can be used in a wider range of conditions. One technology is the solid-state battery that doesn't involve the presence of liquid electrolyte, but rather, a solid electrolyte. Solid electrolytes could be composed of oxide/ceramic materials, sulfide materials or polymer. Also, as the polymer materials are insufficiently conductive to ensure good performances, a combination of different types could be possible; called hybrid solid state electrolyte (Machín et al., 2024).

Figure 1: Types of SSB (Schmaltz et al., 2023)

Among the main types of SSB envisaged (sulfide, polymer, oxide or hybrid), the polymeric type is currently the most studied as shown by the number of patents and the production capacity (Figure 2) (Karkar et al., 2024). However, estimations show that by 2035, solid-state sulfide batteries are likely to gain market share (Schmaltz et al., 2023). Recycling processes will have to adapt to these changes.

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Figure 2: a) Number of patents related to solid-state technology (Karkar et al., 2024) and b) Estimations on SSB production capacity, as forecast by battery experts from industry and academia at a workshop in 2021 see (Schmaltz et al., 2023)

The AM4BAT European project developed a hybrid type solid state battery without anode. This assembly is composed of:

- At anode side, a current collector composed by copper coated silver foil (or tin coated)
- An electrolyte composed of ceramic material LLZO (20 wt.%) or SiO₂ comprised inside a polymer matrix composed of 16 % LiTFSI salt, acrylonitrile, glutaronitrile and TMPTA
- A cathode composed of NMC 811 and polymeric matrix
- And finally, a current collector at cathode side composed by aluminum

Among hybrid or polymer SSB type, the most employed polymeric material for electrolyte is polyethylene oxide (PEO) (Karkar et al., 2024). In recycling processes point of view, the treatment of polymeric electrolyte needs limited precautions compared to other types like sulfide solid electrolyte. But the challenge is that they are often used in hybrid type which makes recycling more difficult and polymer have a limited economical value (Ahuis et al., 2024).

Figure 3: Elementary composition (wt.%) of a conventional LIB and different SSBs at the cell level (Ahuis et al., 2024)

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As shown by *Ahuis et al.*, (Ahuis et al., 2024), the proportion of lithium in all solid-state battery technologies contains on average twice as much Li as in Li-ion batteries (Figure 3). It is therefore essential to also focus on recycling this element.

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1. Overall recycling steps

Recycling strategy has been developed in this report on separate battery materials provided by project partners. Consequently, battery deactivation and dismantling of solid-state cells have not been studied. Regarding the complexity of the cells where layers are printed on each other and further photocured, dismantling process can be more complex than for conventional Li ion technologies. The table below (Table 1) lists the different materials received and used for the recycling study.

Table 1: List of received materials from project partner for task 8.5

Materials	Received on
LLZO powder from AM4BAT	07/2024
1 electrolyte film from Photocentric	09/2024
1 cathode film	09/2024
4 Electrolyte films (LEITAT)	03/2025
Ag/Cu and Cu/Sn current collector (LEITAT)	03/2025
Pieces of electrolyte film with LLZO produced by LEITAT from Justin Bouvet CEA	05/2025
1 pouch-cell AM4BAT anode type from AIT	12/2025
1 pouch-cell "Li-metal" from AIT	12/2025

As the global objective here is to develop a recycling flow sheet as simple as possible, Figure 4 summarizes the developed process based on detailed experimental study on separate materials. The process steps involve the recovery of each component and subsequent treatment of the following components, LiTFSI, LLZO, NMC, Al, Cu and Ag. The following parts of this report will detail each step separately.

Figure 4: Scheme of the overall recycling steps adapted to the mix of separate components of the solid-state battery developed in Am4bat project.

1.1 Battery Deactivation and Dismantling

For safe dismantling of batteries, deactivation is important to ensure safe handling. Though the deactivation step is not to be performed in this project, however, similar to conventional Li ion batteries, deactivation is a prerequisite step to ensure a SOC = 0 V for safety measures. So far, there is very scarce number of publications that deal with the hybrid polymer electrolyte solid state batteries, and the deactivation methods that are designed for conventional Li-ion batteries are considered flexible to accommodate a wide variety of cell and battery designs, chemistries and different forms.

The two main deactivation methods identified in literature includes (Duessenfeld, n.d.; Kang et al., 2025):

- Salt immersion: It enables the discharge of energized cells through immersion in sodium chloride (NaCl) or other solutions. The primary associated hazard is the generation of hydrogen gas during the discharge process.
- Electric discharge: This is a moderately deployed method that is ranked among the safest deactivation techniques due to the absence of hazardous waste generation. The only requirement is proper sizing of the electrical load according to the characteristics of the battery system to be deactivated.

Among deactivation techniques, salt immersion offers the best balance across flexibility, deployability, affordability, and safety considerations. However, electric discharge maintains the highest safety profile of all methods and can potentially be adapted to the hybrid polymer solid-state battery technology.

After the deactivation process, cells could be treated by different physical methods to physically separate material prior chemical treatment. These involve shredding or grinding deactivated cells to reduce particle size and enhance the outcome for the following physical separation steps. Such treatment is considered essential to reduce the treated volume with hydrometallurgical processes. Other physical methods can consist in automated extraction of active materials from the casing which allow also their separation in one step (Colledani et al., 2023).

1.2 LiTFSI selective washing

When considering the electrolyte part, the most valuable element is the Li content. As the polymer used in the electrolyte layer formulation is cross-linked, it's difficult to recover the involved ionomers. Two possible sources of Li are present in the electrolyte layer, either LiTFSI and/or LLZO. If we consider the economical values of each recycled LLZO and LiTFSI, assuming 100 % recovery from EoL cells, they represent 20 times higher value than carbonate precursor of Li. For this main reason, selective leaching of LiTFSI versus that of LLZO is studied. Thanks to the high solubility of LiTFSI in water, this allows its isolation from LLZO. By knowing the dissolution kinetics of Li from both LLZO and LiTFSI, it is possible to isolate LiTFSI separately.

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Table 2: Estimation of financial gains in different scenarios for recovering lithium species present in batteries (Calculated according to Sigma aldrich price for reagent grade products in January 2025) based on the scenario of using LLZO in the electrolyte (as communicated in 2024 at the start of the recycling task)

	Price (euros) for 1g	Mass in 100 g of electrolyte (g)	Case 1 Li recovery	Case2 LiTFSI recovery	Case 3 LiTFSI & LLZO separation & recovery
Li₂CO₃	0.7	13.7	9.6 euros	64 euros	224 euros
LLZO	8	20			
LITFSI	4	16			

For the electrolyte leaching step, also referred as the washing step, a known mass of the electrolyte membrane is added to a known volume of deionized water (S/L = 10 %) while shaking at controlled rotation speed of 400 rpm. Aliquots isolated at different time intervals (0 - 10 min) are first filtered using 0.45 PTFE filters then diluted either with 2 % HNO₃ for ICP-OES or with a deuterated solvent for F¹⁹-NMR analysis. The combination of these two analysis techniques allows to identify the source of Li dissolved in the collected aliquots. More precisely, to determine the total Li content in aliquots, ICP-OES is used and to determine the Li content from LiTFSI only, F¹⁹-NMR is used. As illustrated in Figure 5, the difference in total Li content and that from LiTFSI allows to predict the dissolution behavior of Li from LLZO.

Figure 5: Li analysis techniques used to predict Li dissolution behavior from LiTFSI and LLZO

Electrolytes supplied by both Leitac and Photocentric were tested for the washing steps. No significant effect of washing temperature (2 °C and 25 °C) on the dissolution of LiTFSI was observed as illustrated in Figure 6-a. The reliability of our Li analysis method, as well as its ability to differentiate Li sources, whether from LiTFSI, or LLZO, or both, is confirmed by the results of Figure 6-b. Such that, upon washing of electrolyte films lacking LLZO (Leitac and Photocentric), the calculated Li originating from LLZO is zero.

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Figure 6: Measured Li dissolution from LiTFSI and calculated Li loss from LLZO content in the electrolyte layers provided by Leitac and Photocentric at 2 °C and 25 °C.

Washing of Leitac electrolyte film containing LLZO is performed at room temperature. Results present in Figure 7, shows that for an electrolyte membrane composed of both LiTFSI and LLZO, washing must be controlled at 2 mins to ensure complete solubilization of LiTFSI while avoiding Li depletion from the LLZO structure. According to Figure 7-b, the amount of Li solubilized from LLZO is close to 20% of the total Li initially present in the LLZO material and remains constant even after 30 minutes of washing.

In fact, in water *Schneider et al.*, (Schneider et al., 2023) indicate that the exchange between Li^+ and H^+ can causes Li loss from garnet LLZO structure and the formation of LiOH (Equation 1). Consequently, the Li leaching in water in their case is up to 60% after 3 hours.

Figure 7: Measured Li dissolution from LiTFSI and calculated Li loss from LLZO content in the LEITAT electrolyte layer containing LLZO 25 °C.

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To understand the influence of the washing step on LLZO, raw LLZO powder used by the project members for the electrolyte formulation, was washed in water. The dissolution of Li and Al from raw LLZO powder as a function of washing time, was compared to that present within the photocured electrolyte (LLZO with LiTFSI & polymer). According to the dissolution behavior presented in Figure 8, we can observe that Li and Al dissolution from LLZO is shifted to higher times once LLZO is presented within the electrolyte complex. This signifies that the diffusion slows down the Li and Al leaching from LLZO once its present within the electrolyte.

Figure 8: Comparison of Li and Al leaching kinetics between Torrecid LLZO powder (filled bars) and LLZO inside Leitac electrolyte (dashed bars)

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1.3 Physical separation steps: Sieving and electrolyte density flotation

The density of electrolyte sheet has been estimated experimentally at around 1.2 g/cm^3 . Due to its low density compared to other parts ($\text{Al } 2.7 > \text{NMC } 4.8 > \text{CC around } 9$) and its density close the density of water, it is possible to realize a dense media separation using water-based solution. The salt added in water must be compatible with the electrolyte, environmentally friendly, safe and be highly soluble. Moreover, the addition of this salt in water must allow obtaining a density of solution higher than the polymer one. MgSO_4 salt has been chosen for these reasons. At an industrial scale, dry processes could be envisaged as they are simpler and cheaper. For example, zig zag air separators.

Here, a solution of Mg_2SO_4 of 1.3 density has been prepared. For the proof of concept, the same surface of electrolyte, cathode sheet, aluminum and copper-silver foil have been manually mixed in a vial with the Mg_2SO_4 solution. After less than 5 seconds, the electrolyte sheet rises to the surface and stays at least 30 minutes without re-sinking (Figure 9). This proof of concept shows that polymer electrolyte could be efficiently and easily separated from metallic parts by a sink-float process with a low-cost and environmentally friendly water-based solution.

Figure 9: Dense media flotation of electrolyte membrane

1.4 LLZO recovery

After the LiTFSI washing step, almost all LiTFSI content is removed from the polymer and low quantities of Al, La and Li are leached from LLZO during this process. Consequently, electrolyte sheet contains only polymer and LLZO. Prior thermal treatment, TGA measurements realized before and after LiTFSI washing (Figure 10) indicated that there is no significant mass loss after 500°C . Also, the difference in weight loss between the two samples between 100 and 500°C could be explained by either losses in LiTFSI content, monomers or modification of hydration content. To ensure the full degradation of the polymer and following thermal treatment for LLZO synthesis, the thermal treatment for LLZO recovery consists in 700°C during 6 hours under pressurized air atmosphere.

An electrolyte piece of around 0.03 g has been treated following this protocol. After thermal treatment, the residual powder is analyzed by XRD in order to evaluate its mineralogical form and compared it with the reference one (LLZO synthesized by *Torreacid* in Am4BAT project).

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Figure 10: Raw Leitat electrolyte and LiTFSI washed Leitat sample TGA analysis between 20 and 900°C with a heat speed of 5°C/min in air atmosphere.

XRD analysis presented in Figure 11 shows that it's not feasible with this treatment to recover exactly the same powder as the initial one. In fact, the initial LLZO powder (*Torreced*) contains Al doped LLZO into two forms: $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ and $\text{Li}_{6.55}\text{Al}_{0.15}\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ which represent respectively around 36 % and 25% of mineralogical identified species. Also, *Torreced* powder contains simple oxides like ZrO_2 which can come from precursors used for LLZO synthesis. After treatment, simple oxides forms and Al doped forms are not identified. Finally, a form without Li has been identified with an occurrence of around 30 %. This signify that part of Li has been lost during the treatment (LiTFSI washing and/or thermal treatment). During LLZO synthesis, lithiation should be performed during this step with Li_2CO_3 addition during thermal treatment. Calculations of La, Li and Al loss percentages based on XRD results reveals that around 25 % of initial Li, 100 % of initial Al and 17% of initial La seems to be lost during washing and/or calcination. A shorter washing treatment time could be used to limit Al and Li leaching and relithiation steps could be added during the calcination to improve the quality of the recovered material.

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Figure 11: XRD spectrum of Torrecid LLZO powder and calcinated washed electrolyte

1.5 Recovery of metallic components: Al, Cu, Sn, Ag

Option 1: selective leaching in 2 steps

Due to the presence of three different metals, reductions and oxidations could be linked to the presence of these three components. For example, in ammoniacal solution, copper could be easily dissolved due to the formation of stable and soluble copper complexes as Cu (NH₃)₄²⁺ for example. Nevertheless, oxidized copper could be directly reduced on aluminum surface or

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tin surface (Figure 12). This cementation phenomenon is classically used for copper recovery on iron or aluminum. To avoid this cementation, tin and aluminum have to be leached first.

Figure 12: Oxidation reduction potential to explain the leaching reactions than can occur in presence of Cu, Al, Ag and Sn

Two types of current collectors were provided for recycling demonstration, Al-Ag-Cu and Al-Sn-Cu. As commonly known in literature, selective leaching of Al is commonly carried out in basic solution, namely with NaOH. However, it was observed herein, that Al leaching in the presence of Sn is challenging, and unlike demonstrated by Pourbaix diagram, Al removal at pH 9 is accompanied by 30 % of Sn content. Selectivity can be improved if operational parameter as well as leaching media is optimized, however, as the current collector of Am4bat SSB will probably be composed of Al-Ag-Cu collector, experiments are focalized on the latter. At pH 10.3, after 20 hours of leaching at room temperature, all Al foil has been solubilized and the cathodic current collector is still entire (Figure 13-a)). ICP-OES analysis of aliquots at different times certifies the complete solubilization of Al.

Then, the residual Cu-Ag coated foil is treated in ammonium medium composed of 1.25M of NH_4OH and 1.25M NH_4Cl at room temperature in an agitated medium. After less than 5 hours, all copper has been leached and less than 4% of Ag have been solubilized (Figure 13-b). Leaching conditions could be optimized to improve selectivity of this leaching step for example by modifying the ratio NH_4OH and NH_4Cl which modify the solution pH. The residual material is then composed of 100 % Ag (Figure 13-c).

Another perspective for the recycling of this mix of current collectors could be leaching in acidic media namely HCl. In fact, in this chlorinated environment, allow the leaching of Al and Cu while silver is stabilized in the AgCl solid. The leaching solution could be, after filtration, be treated by electrowinning for Cu recovery.

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Figure 13: Leaching kinetics of Al and Cu during leaching steps and picture of silver residual sheet

Option 2: Non-selective leaching step and electrochemical recovery of copper

The second option consists of a leaching step in HCl media. In this media, copper and Al are easily solubilized and Ag is insoluble. Ag could be then recovered by filtration and the remain copper-aluminum solution is used in electrodeposition for copper recovery.

First, solid mix of Al cc and Cu cc is placed on HCl solution 2.9 M at 80°C under magnetic stirring with a solid/liquid ratio of 10 wt.%. After 15 min, H₂O₂ 10% vol. is added for a total concentration of 5.3 vol.% of H₂O₂ 10 vol.% After 45 min of leaching, the solution is cooled down and filtered on 0.45 μm porosity filter under vacuum to recover solid silver.

The recovered solution is then placed in an electrochemical cell of 100 mL volume (50 mL used) composed of 3 electrodes (Figure 14). The reference electrode made of Ag/AgCl (RE), one working electrode (WE) made of stainless steel and one counter electrode (CE) in platinum. The copper deposit takes place on the stainless-steel electrode which represent 1 cm² surface for the deposit.

For the proof of concept, a 2 hour experiment is made. After this time, the WE is recovered and washed with DIW. The dendritic deposit detaches easily from its support.

Figure 14: Schematic diagram of the electrochemical cell for copper electrodeposition

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Quantification of the useful energy used at the deposition of copper can be done by calculating faradic efficiency (η) as follow (Equation 1):

$$\eta = \frac{Q_{tot}}{Q_{reac}} \cdot 100\% \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Based on chronoamperometry (Figure 15), the Q_{total} is calculated by integrating the measured current over a period of time (herein 1,5 hours) (Equation 3).

$$Q_{tot} = \int_0^t I(t) dt \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Based on ICP-OES measurement of copper concentration in solution and the copper deposition equation (Equation 2), Q_{reac} is calculated as follow (Equation 4):

$$Q_{reac} = n \cdot F \cdot N \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

With n the number of consumed electrons here 2 electrons are consumed for 1 copper, F the Faraday constant (96 485 C/mol) and N the number of copper moles deposited

Calculations:

$$Q_{tot} = \int_0^t I(t) dt = 63.066 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{h}$$

$$Q_{reac} = n \cdot F \cdot N = 2 * 96\,485 * \left(\frac{20.2 \cdot 10^{-3}}{63.546} \right) = 61.34 \text{ mA} \cdot \text{h}$$

$$\eta = \frac{Q_{reac}}{Q_{tot}} \cdot 100\% = \frac{61.34}{63.066} = 97.3\%$$

This result means that 97.3 % of the energy is used to deposit copper, i.e., 2.7 % is used for other reactions such as the reduction of other species such as nickel.

Figure 15 : Chronoamperometry graph for copper deposition from Cu/Ag/Al solution produced by dissolution in HCl 2.9 M and H₂O₂ solution of Ag/Cu and Al current collectors

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1.6 Cathode layer treatment

Cathode layer recycling was studied following two technical proposals:

- the classically used hydrometallurgy process including leaching and various types of separatives steps
- the thermal treatment to take advantage of the high purity of the insulated cathode film

1.6.1 Hydrometallurgical pathway: chemical treatment for the recovery of Mn, Ni and Co

The collected NMC powder, obtained after the primary washing step to isolate LiTFSI from the separated components, is treated via hydrometallurgy to recover metals of interest. This type of treatment is well investigated in literature and widely use even by industrial plants for recycling of Li-ion batteries active materials. A known mass of NMC powder is added to a hot sulfuric acid solution at pH 0.7 and 80 °C. The pH of the system is monitored throughout the experiment and automatically adjusted to pH 1 using a *Metrohm* titration *pH-stat* system. To ensure complete dissolution of the metals, hydrogen peroxide 10 vol.% is manually added to the system (10 vol.%).

To determine the dissolution kinetics of each element, sample aliquots are taken at specific time intervals and then analyzed by ICP-OES. As shown in Figure 16, the leaching yields observed after 5 h at 80°C are 81% of initial Ni, 86% Li, 72% Co, and 72% Mn. These values could be improved by increasing quantities of hydrogen peroxide.

Figure 16: Results of NMC leaching during 24h at 80°C in H_2SO_4 media at regulated pH of pH 0.7 with addition of 10 % vol. H_2O_2 30% – from ICP-OES analysis of samples

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In literature, there are several methods for the separation of these metal (Li, Ni, Co, Mn). Depending on the quality of targeted salts, either solvent extraction, selective precipitation or simple precipitation with conventional bases can be used. In certain cases, a mix of several technologies can be used to ensure the production of high purity salts. In this work, as no KPI is fixed for salt production nor their relative purities we considered basic precipitation method used for the LCA work published by *Karunanayakage and Lanka* (Karunanayakage and Lanka, 2025) in their work, report that Co is the first element to precipitate out of the leachate at pH6, then Ni at Ph 7-8 then Mn at pH 8-9. The remaining solution containing Li is then treated with Na_2CO_3 to obtain Li_2CO_3 .

In any case, these issues have not been explored in depth, as the steps are the same as those widely developed for the recycling of lithium-ion batteries.

1.6.2 Direct recycling: thermal treatment for the recovery of NMC particles

Post sieving step, NMC is recovered without any pollution, for this reason thermal treatment could be sufficient to remove the polymeric content and directly recover NMC powder. The studied materials herein have not been cycled, thus no chemical or structural modification of NMC particles are to be observed. On the contrary, cycled materials undergo chemical and structural modification, this thermal treatment won't be sufficient.

As the battery manufacturing industry generates more than 50 % production scrap, making this direct recycling a widely studied and economically viable approach for cathode active material recovery and valorization. Herein, we investigated this methodology and evaluated the morphological characteristics of the recovered NMC cathode material via scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the structural form using X-ray diffraction (XRD).

The collected NMC powder is thermally treated at 700°C for 2 h in an argon atmosphere to prevent particle oxidation. This thermal treatment facilitated the removal of organic residues and yielded carbon-free NMC particles. The XRD pattern of the recovered particles (Figure 17) matched that of the pristine NMC powder, confirming that thermal treatment preserved the crystalline structure identical to the original material (PDF file 04-026-2977). These results demonstrate that the recovery process maintains the structural integrity and phase purity of the NMC material without inducing unwanted crystalline phase transformations.

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Figure 17: XRD pattern of NMC particles after thermal treatment under Ar atmosphere (700 °C, 2 h).

Microscopic imaging (Figure 18) of the recovered powder revealed a spherical particle structure characteristic of NMC material, with some minor surface cracks that may have resulted from mechanical grinding during sample preparation for morphological characterization. The size of the particle is around 10 μm .

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Figure 18: SEM snapshots of NMC particles after thermal treatment under Ar atmosphere (700 °C, 2 h).

1.7 Conclusions

To conclude the general flowsheet for treatments of a mix of separate layers from AM4BAT partners is presented with incomes and outcomes in the Figure 19. Generated and valuable components are:

- LiTFSI rich solution which has to be purified from monomers residues.
- NMC particles with good specifications
- LLZO powder which requires a partial relithiation step
- Al rich solution
- Metallic copper
- Silver metallic foil

The following table (Table 3) lists the estimated global maximal recoveries obtained for each outcome and the global Li recovery rate is calculated as follow :

$$\frac{(m_{LiTFSI} * \%Li_{in LiTFSI}) * R_{LiTFSI} + (m_{LLZO} * \%Li_{in LLZO}) * R_{LLZO} + (m_{NMC} * \%Li_{in NMC}) * R_{NMC}}{(m_{LiTFSI} * \%Li_{in LiTFSI}) + (m_{LLZO} * \%Li_{in LLZO}) + (m_{NMC} * \%Li_{in NMC})} = 92 \%$$

With :

m_{LiTFSI} the initial LiTFSI mass used for one cell

m_{LLZO} the initial LLZO mass used for one cell

m_{NMC} the initial LLZO mass used for one cell

R_{LiTFSI} the recovery rate for LiTFSI

R_{LLZO} the recovery rate for LLZO

R_{NMC} the recovery rate for LLZO

$Li\%_{in LiTFSI}$ percentage of Li in LiTFSI structure (2.42 %)

$\%Li_{in LLZO}$ the percentage of Li in LLZO structure (5.79%)

$\%Li_{in NMC}$ the percentage of Li in LLZO structure (7.13%)

The Global recovery rates calculated herein is 92 % for Li, 95 % for Co and Ni, and 99 % for Cu. Depending on the refinement processes applied further for Co/Ni/Mn separation these recovery rate can be impacted. However, the values recovered herein satisfy the EU targets for 2031 (80 % for Li and 95 % % for Ni, Co and Cu)(THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT and THE COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION, 2023).

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Table 3 : Estimation of components recoveries

	Delamination	LiTFSI washing	Sieving	Sink float	Al leaching	Cu leaching	Cu electrodeposition	cathode pyrolysis	LLZO calcination	total recoveries
Al	100%	x	100%	100%	100%	x	x	x	x	100%
Cu	100%	x	100%	100%	x	100%	99%	x	x	99%
Ag	100%	x	100%	100%	x	x	x	x	x	100%
NMC	100%	x	100%	x	x	x	x	95%	x	95%
LiTFSI	100%	85%	X	x	x	x	x	x	x	85%
LLZO	100%	x	100%	100%	x	x	x	x	90%	90%

Figure 19 : global recycling flowsheet developed on mix of separate materials

2 Proof of concept on AM4BAT pouch cell

Two pouch-cells have been sent by AIT to realize a proof of concept of the whole recycling process from dismantling to separate elements production. These two cells have been received on December 2nd 2025. Consequently, these steps could not be optimized. The cell with the AM4BAT composition has been chosen, it consists of an assembly of a cathode, an electrolyte, and current collectors packaged in a flexible container. With a size of 14x12 cm and an active layer's surface of approximately 4x5 cm (Figure 20). No detailed information was provided. Subsequent analysis revealed that the electrolyte used is loaded with SiO₂ and not LLZO, as it was the case in the previously tested materials. The current collector on the anode side is composed of Cu-Sn and not Cu-Ag. No information on the tests potentially performed with this battery has been provided.

Figure 20 : Picture of treated pouch-cell from AIT

2.1 Opening

After ensuring that the object was completely discharged (0 V), the cell was opened manually (Figure 21). This step can be performed automatically for larger objects with automated extraction of the active layers. Here, the cell is cut, open and the external current collectors are separated to leave only the active layers. The whole assembly is soaked in a large volume of water to remove any traces of metallic Li and also to carry out the LiTFSI washing step.

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Figure 21 : pictures of opening step

2.2 LiTFSI washing and delamination

After the opening step, the use of deionized water bath allows the LiTFSI washing as shown in section 1.2. Here, the step duration was longer than what had been done in the previous section on separate materials; around 10 minutes. During this step, the anode side current collector came off quickly then the Al current collector detached as well as NMC cathode layer which begins to break off into small fragments, as observed during tests on separate materials. All these layers are then filtrated to recover the LiTFSI charged solution. Its color is pale yellow and slightly viscous. After a drying stage to concentrate the solution, 50 mL are recovered and then analyzed by ^{19}F NMR and ICP-OES to estimate the proportion of LiTFSI recovered and any impurities present. After this filtration stage, particles are placed back in deionized water in order to promote cathode-electrolyte detachment. To promote their detachment, the suspension is placed 2x30 min in ultrasounds bath at 30 kHz. This effectively removed a large portion of the NMC particles from the surface of the electrolyte, although some particles remained attached after this treatment. This treatment also made it possible to detach a large portion of the cathode fragments adhering to the surface of the aluminum current collector, but it also caused holes in the aluminum current collector (Figure 22). This solution is recovered and analyzed also by ^{19}F NMR and ICP-OES (named NMC washing) (Table 4).

Table 4 : Synthesis of NMR and ICP-OES results on LiTFSI washing solution and NMC washing solution

	[LiTFSI] in g/L measured by NMR ^{19}F	Volume (L)	Repartition of LiTFSI	Li total mass in mg from ICP-OES measurements
LiTFSI Washing	2.94	0.05	87 %	3.08
NMC washing	0.067	0.35	13 %	0.52

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Figure 22: Recovered layers after ultrasounds treatment A- Al current collector with in red dotted line residual cathode fragments and red arrows holes formed by ultrasonic processing, B- Cu current collector and C- electrolyte layer with residual cathode particles in black

2.3 Sieving

To separate layers and NMC particles that have broken off into fragments, the step of sieving is realized with the water suspension of layers in water on 1 mm sieve (Figure 23). Water charged with cathode particles is filtered on 0,45 μm filter under vacuum. Recovered layers are then placed into sink-float bath.

Figure 23: Picture of 1 mm sieve during sieving step

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2.4 Sink-float

Sink-float step is used here to allow the separation of polymer layer which has a density close to 1 comparatively with metallic compounds. For that, a solution of $MgSO_4$, a nontoxic and inexpensive salt with a good solubility in water at room temperature, with a density of 1.25 g/mL minimum is used. The Figure 24(a) shows the upward movement of electrolyte film recovered on the sieve. In less than 5 seconds after manual mixing of layers in the salt solution, the electrolyte film is on top of the solution while the other layers remain at the bottom of the solution. At industrial scale, big tanks with mixing and scrapping system are used, especially for plastics sorting as illustrated in Figure 24(b).

Figure 24 : a- sink-float step on small pieces of layers from sieving step at different times after mixing and b- illustration of sink-float step for industrial plastic sorting from B+B Anlagenbau company

2.5 Current collectors recycling

2.5.1 Current collectors leaching

As presented in the first part of this report, one of the options for current collector recovery could be HCl leaching, which allows selective leaching of Cu and Al without Ag leaching in the case of Ag-Cu CC. In the case of Cu-Sn CC, this leaching step isn't selective, but electrodeposition of copper could selectively separate this element.

Layers are placed in a flask containing a 2.9 M HCl solution at 80°C under magnetic agitation with a classical cooling system. After stabilization of 15 minutes, 10 vol.% H₂O₂ is added for a total of 5.3 vol.% of 10% vol. H₂O₂. After H₂O₂ addition, the solution turns green very rapidly without any residual solids (Figure 25). In this pouch-cell, the anode CC used is composed of Cu-Sn. Consequently, this leaching step leaches all metals and isn't selective.

Figure 25: Leaching solution of Cu-Sn and Al current collectors in HCl+H₂O₂ media

2.5.2 Copper electrodeposition

One of the easiest methods to recover selectively copper in metallic form without modifying solution pH or composition is electrodeposition. As described in section 1.5, a 3 electrodes setup is employed in a 100 mL specific glass container to realize a copper deposit on top of the WE in stainless steel. A tension of -0.35 V (vs Ag/AgCl) is kept constant during the experiment

(chronoamperometry). Four samples have been taken during the experiment to estimate the selectivity of this method towards Sn and Al and to estimate the copper recovery (Figure 27). 5 hours and 40 minutes of experiments have been conducted. During this time, Sn, Ni and Ag concentrations remains stables while the copper concentration decreases. The ICP-OES of dissolved deposit shows a copper deposit purity of

Figure 26: XRD spectrum of copper deposit

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99.55% with impurities coming from Ag and Sn but also probably from Ni and Mn as shown in WRD spectrum (Figure 26) which may originate from external pollution from the electrodeposition cell.

Figure 27: Copper electrodeposition results. a-SEM snapshots of copper deposit after 5h40 in secondary electrons. b-composition of remaining solution during copper electrodeposition based on ICP-EOS analysis of samples and pictures of copper deposits at different deposition times

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2.5.3 NMC recovery

The recovered NMC particles detached after LiTFSI washing step and after ultrasounds treatment are treated in NaOH 2M solution during 5 hours at 50°C in order to remove Al which comes from the holes formed in Al cc during ultrasounds treatment. This step could be removed if the sink-float step is performed before the ultrasonic release of the NMC. After this treatment, the solution is centrifugated during 10 min at 40 krpm and the remaining solution is kept for ICP-EOS analysis. The NMC powder is washed 3 times with 50 mL and centrifugated each time. The washing solution is also analyzed by ICP-OES. The remaining solid is dried at 80°C and then analyzed by XRD and SEM observations.

Figure 28: SEM snapshots in secondary electrons mode of NMC particles after Al removal treatment in NaOH solution

SEM snapshots show that NMC structure is preserved with this typical raspberry shape. On the other hand, very small particles (<1 µm) are also visible on snapshots as well as flakes particles with smooth surface. Small particles could be Al and/or NMC leaching products like Al_2O_3 . Flake particles could be residues of electrolyte polymer parts.

XRD spectrum (Figure 29) shows that this powder is mainly composed of NMC type oxides and small proportion of carbon (around 8%) which confirms the presence of electrolyte residues.

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Figure 29: XRD spectrum of recovered NMC particles

This solid can therefore be treated either by conventional hydrometallurgical methods involving leaching followed by purification and separate precipitation of the oxides, or by the shorter thermal method tested previously. The latter has not been tested, but given the composition of this fraction as determined by XRD, it is likely that the polymer residues will be degraded and that the purity of the fraction will be sufficient after treatment. The treatment temperature will probably need to be adjusted in order to preserve as much as possible the raspberry structure of the NMC particles.

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2.6 SiO₂ recovery

As for the recycling treatment developed on separate materials, the electrolyte layer is recovered after sink-float step to realize a calcination. This step allows the degradation of polymer to keep only the remaining LLZO or₂. Unlike the ideal case with separate materials, the mixture of electrolyte and cathode that is visible before treatment is found after treatment with the presence of a gray coloration of the calcined powder coming from the NMC particles, which are clearly visible in the SEM snapshots (red circles on Figure 30). Part of recovered powder is solubilized in Aqua regia at 110°C for 12 hours and then analyzed by ICP-OES to quantify NMC pollution. Also, powder is analyzed by WRD. The results of these two characterization techniques estimates NMC pollution of around 41 % in mass according to ICP-OES result and 46.2% according to XRD semi-quantification into the form mainly of Co nickel oxide, manganese nickel oxide and lithium cobalt nickel oxide (Figure 31). This pollution has to be managed to allow a recovery of pure materials. For that, the particle size difference between LLZO and NMC can be used to achieve separation by size/density. In the case of silica, material value is lower than in the case of LLZO. It is therefore not essential to try to recover it, but rather to promote the recovery of the NMC.

Figure 30: Recovered electrolyte film after calcination (700°C-6h under air) – a- and b- SEM snapshots in secondary electrons, red circles highlight NMC particles and c- picture of calcinated electrolyte film

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Figure 31: XRD spectrum of calcinated electrolyte film after washing and sink-float steps

2.7 Mass balance

When considering the treatment of these small pouch cells, it is evident that the casing constitutes a very large proportion of the battery's mass (91%) (Figure 33). If only the active components are considered, the cathode accounts for 19% of the total, the electrolyte 19%, the aluminum (Al) current collector 14%, and the copper-tin (Cu-Sn) current collector 48%. LiTFSI is first recovered in the washing solution. NMR ¹⁹F analysis indicates a LiTFSI recovery yield of approximately 87%. A sieving step then allows the separation of detached NMC fragments. However, contrary to observations on isolated materials, the polymerization of the two layers (electrolyte and cathode) together results in some NMC remaining adhered to the electrolyte surface. Additionally, part of the cathode remains attached to the aluminum foil edges, likely due to the pressure applied during assembly. The recovered NMC fraction is treated with 2 M NaOH at 50°C for 5 hours to remove aluminum residues from the ultrasonic treatment. The treated fraction weighs 0.1934 g with a purity of around 91% (carbon contamination). After calcination, approximately 41% of the silica fraction consists of NMC, resulting in an overall NMC recovery yield close to 93%. A sink-float separation is then applied. In less than 30 seconds and with good temporal stability, the electrolyte layer rises to the solution surface, enabling its separation from the current collector (CC) layers. After calcination, the remaining solid consists of a mixture of SiO₂ and NMC. These particles, depending on their size, could be separated by decantation or neglected due to their minimal quantity.

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Hydrometallurgical steps are subsequently used to separate the current collector layers. Colorimetric or chemical online detection could easily distinguish aluminum from Sn-Cu layers. This method can also be considered, and may also be considered in the case of lithium-ion batteries pretreatment. In HCl and H₂O₂ media, Sn, Al, and Cu are solubilized within minutes. Copper is then recovered by electrodeposition, achieving a deposit purity of 99.55 % (as determined by ICP-OES analysis of the dissolved deposit) and a recovery rate of 67 % after 5 hours and 40 minutes. This efficiency could be improved by increasing the working electrode (WE) surface area and/or extending the deposition time. Theoretically, Sn could also be electrodeposited in HCl media, as demonstrated by *Herrera-Loya et al.* (Herrera-Loya et al., 2022) in a second step. Also, by increasing the pH above 1, Sn must be precipitated. Globally, the valued elements are:

- LiTFSI have been extracted with a yield of 87% in washing solution and has to be concentrated or crystalized.
- NMC has been recovered in a 91% purity fraction with a yield of 93%. The purity will be increased by thermal treatment and recovery could be improved by suppression SiO₂ recovery step from the spent electrolyte
- Copper is recovered and the electrodeposition yield is classically of 99% with a purity measured here of 99.55%
- Ag could be recovered as insoluble metal and Sn could be theoretically deposited after copper electrodeposition
- No Al recovery has been envisaged here but if Cu and Sn (or Ag) have sufficiently low concentrations in the residual electroplating solution, aluminum can be recovered by precipitation by adjusting the pH, Al precipitates at a pH above 4.

The total recovery in active materials mass is around 78%, and that of Ag or Sn recovery is 99%. Al recovery can improve this yield since it represents 14% by mass of the active materials. By the end of 2027, 90% of cobalt, copper, lead, and nickel and 50% of lithium must be recovered from collected batteries, according to the battery regulation. The Li recovery has been calculated as the sum of LiTFSI recovery multiplied by the percentage of total Li in LiTFSI

Figure 33: Adequacy of recoveries achieved with European regulation

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and the NMC recovery multiplied by the percentage of total Li in NMC. The results are shown in Figure 32: Adequacy of recoveries achieved with European regulation

battery parts		Mass (g)		% total	% without casing
Casing and external current collectors		10,3	10,3	91%	-
Cathode cc	Al	0,1397	0,1397	1%	14%
Cathode film	NMC	0,1934	0,1934	2%	19%
Electrolyte film	LiTFSI		0,1469	1%	15%
	Si(+NMC)	0,186	0,0307	0%	3%
	polymer calcination (gaz)		0,0084	0%	1%
Anode cc	Cu	0,4808	0,231	2%	23%
	Sn		0,25	2%	25%

Figure 34: Mass balance and Sankey diagram representing the masses at each stage of processing

General conclusions

In this work, we demonstrated the recyclability of solid-state batteries developed within the framework of the European project AM4BAT. Unlike conventional lithium-ion batteries currently available on the market, the electrolyte in these batteries is composed of polymer-LiTFSI combined with either SiO₂ or LLZO. Additionally, the anode-free system means that no graphite or metallic lithium is incorporated during battery manufacturing. These fundamental differences necessitate adaptations to current lithium-ion battery recycling processes. To separately recover LiTFSI, a washing step should be added first, and purification steps are likely necessary. Traditionally, crushing is adopted as the initial step to physically separate all layers, which leads to a mixture of all components that must then be separated. If this approach is applied to all-solid-state batteries, similar issues to those encountered with LIBs will arise, such as residual metal contamination from current collectors (typically separated upstream using physical separation techniques) or a loss of lithium, which subsequently reduces its recoverable value. Therefore, it is advantageous for this process to perform separation steps on entire packs without using grinding, since it has been demonstrated that the layers separate easily in an aqueous medium and can then be processed according to their specific characteristics (density for the electrolyte or size for the NMC, which fragments).

If solid-state batteries are mixed with Li-ion batteries in current processing schemes, the presence of polymers could interfere with some stages, particularly the graphite separation stages using flotation. The recovery of certain streams would be impossible because they are too diluted or mixed; this is the case of LiTFSI and LLZO. However, NMC recovery could be adapted to current processes without major modifications.

The total recovery in active materials mass is around 78%, and that of Ag or Sn recovery is 99%. AI recovery can improve this yield since it represents 14% by mass of the active materials. By the end of 2027, 90% of cobalt, copper, lead, and nickel and 50% of lithium must be recovered from collected batteries, according to the battery regulation. The Li recovery has been calculated as the sum of LiTFSI recovery multiplied by the percentage of total Li in LiTFSI and the NMC recovery multiplied by the percentage of total Li in NMC. The results are shown in Figure 32: Adequacy of recoveries achieved with European regulation

References

- Ahuis, M., Doose, S., Vogt, D., Michalowski, P., Zellmer, S., Kwade, A., 2024. Recycling of solid-state batteries. *Nat Energy* 9, 373–385. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-024-01463-4>
- Colledani, M., Gentilini, L., Mossali, E., Picone, N., 2023. A novel mechanical pre-treatment process-chain for the recycling of Li-Ion batteries. *CIRP Annals* 72, 17–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2023.04.068>
- Duessenfeld, n.d. Comparison of different processes for recycling Lithium-Ion Batteries.
- Herrera-Loya, M.R., Cervantes-Herrera, L.M., Gutierrez-Vallejo, S., Ibanez, J.G., 2022. Leaded or unleaded? Homemade microscale tin electroplating. *Chemistry Teacher International* 4, 97–102. <https://doi.org/10.1515/cti-2021-0024>
- Kang, F., Zhao, Y., Liu, Y., Shen, J., Liu, W., Lv, W., Cao, T., Cao, H., Sun, Z., 2025. Discharge Pathways and Deactivation Mechanisms of Retired Lithium-Ion Batteries. *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* 13, 5985–5995. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.5c00940>
- Karkar, Z., Houache, M.S.E., Yim, C.-H., Abu-Lebdeh, Y., 2024. An Industrial Perspective and Intellectual Property Landscape on Solid-State Battery Technology with a Focus on Solid-State Electrolyte Chemistries. *Batteries* 10, 24. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries10010024>
- Karunanayakage, M., Lanka, E., 2025. Life Cycle Assessment(LCA) of Nickel, Manganese, Cobalt, (NMC) Batteries: Sustainability through Advanced Processes.
- Machín, A., Cotto, M.C., Díaz, F., Duconge, J., Morant, C., Márquez, F., 2024. Environmental Aspects and Recycling of Solid-State Batteries: A Comprehensive Review. *Batteries* 10, 255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries10070255>
- Schmaltz, T., Hartmann, F., Wicke, T., Weymann, L., Neef, C., Janek, J., 2023. A Roadmap for Solid-State Batteries. *Advanced Energy Materials* 13, 2301886. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202301886>
- Schneider, K., Kiyek, V., Finsterbusch, M., Yagmurlu, B., Goldmann, D., 2023. Acid Leaching of Al- and Ta-Substituted $\text{Li}_7\text{La}_3\text{Zr}_2\text{O}_{12}$ (LLZO) Solid Electrolyte. *Metals* 13, 834. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13050834>
- THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION, 2023. REGULATION (EU) 2023/1542 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 12 July 2023 concerning batteries and waste batteries, amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU)2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC ANNEX XII STORAGE AND TREATMENT, INCLUDING RECYCLING, REQUIREMENTS- Part C: Targets for recovery of materials.